

Gorenstein Projective, Injective and Flat Modules Relative to Semidualizing Modules

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Abstract : In this paper we study some properties of GC- projective, injective and flat modules, where C is a semidualizing module and we discuss some connections between GC-projective, injective and flat modules, and we consider these properties under change of rings such that completions of rings, Morita equivalences and the localizations.

Keywords : Semidualizing module; C-projective(injective,flat); GC-projective (injective,flat); Commutative ring; Localizations

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